

Modulating Users' Involvement in Interactive Machine Learning Solutions: A Model Cascade Strategy

Oihane Gómez-Carmona¹, Diego Casado-Mansilla², Diego López-de-Ipiña²,
and Javier García-Zubia²

¹ DeustoTech - University of Deusto, Bilbao, Spain, oihane.gomez@deusto.es

² Faculty of Engineering - University of Deusto, Bilbao, Spain
{dcasado,dipina,zubia}@deusto.es

Abstract. Adapting intelligent systems to the end-user goals and their desire for involvement is essential when designing trustworthy interactive solutions. In intelligent environments, where sensitive information must be preserved, the challenge becomes two-fold: i) approaching the critical personal data to the user to promote privacy (i.e., Edge Computing); and ii) adaptatively modulating users' participation throughout the time. For this reason, this work proposes an interactive approach based on a cascade of Machine Learning models that makes optimized decisions related to classifying individual data and labelling it. For the evaluated use-case of a Human Activity Recognition system, the initial quantitative results of the proposed strategy show that an interactive cascade of simpler models can improve the non-interactive approach used as a benchmark and, at the same time, modulate the degree of participation of the user, measured as the number of times they would be inquired to provide a new label for newly obtained data. Thus, this paper provides insights into how this approach may be used in designing intelligent systems to adapt to the role of users in the personalization of intelligent models and how to build flexible experiences and learning systems where the user feels involved. All this while maintaining the privacy requirements that apply to Edge Intelligence and Edge Computing concepts.

Keywords: Interactive Machine Learning · Model Cascade · Optimization · Edge Computing · Edge Intelligence.

1 Introduction

Current Internet of Things (IoT) architectures and frameworks usually neglect the degree of confidence and involvement humans require to adopt these technologies in their everyday lives [1]. Besides, in intelligent environments, trust concerns are critical issues that affect the technology acceptance and the engagement of the users [25]. Thus, future smart spaces must ensure the privacy of the captured information and empower the role of end-users by giving them increased control over the system and their data [22]. When the confidence in

the technology is highly dependent on the privacy of the information it captures, it becomes more logical to place at a local stage as much analytical power as possible since data is generated at the sensors close to the user, as Edge Computing proposes [26]. Nonetheless, despite the possibilities offered by modern hardware platforms to host such applications, the limitations of the computational capabilities of the Edge and end-devices hinder the execution of intelligent solutions, and, particularly Machine Learning (ML) techniques on them [7]. Thus, the technological challenges of integrating such demanding tasks at the Edge involve optimizing classification tasks to be embedded on resource-constrained devices [20].

Nevertheless, making the Edge genuinely intelligent requires the creation of spaces where human and machine intelligence may cooperate and interact. This entails building human-centered scenarios in which the system may learn from its end-users to become more successful [2]. For this reason, to make ML more helpful and usable, a human-centered approach should rethink its functioning in terms of human objectives, situations, and preferences [10]. In this respect, Interactive ML (IML) techniques involve human-in-the-loop in the classification process by providing the user more influence over the system, allowing end-users to adapt and configure systems independently [3]. However, user engagement levels may vary depending on the context, time, and task, and various end users may have varying levels of involvement [19]. That is, the ability to configure and change the system once it is launched necessitates frequent model updates. This is especially challenging when intelligent solutions must be reduced in size and complexity while at the same time adapting their behavior to the preferences of the users.

For this reason, in this work, we present a novel interactive approach that combines performance optimization with personalized ML in an Edge Computing approach. This approach adapts the model cascade optimization technique presented in [12] to an interactive scenario that modulates the number of times the user may be queried to label new data instances. This way, users participate in the model fitting by providing new annotated data when inquired by the system. For that, this approach matches the confidence thresholds that rule the classification cascade with the user’s desired participation level. Depending on these thresholds, the cascade could provide the most probable prediction for a new data sequence or ask the user about its corresponding label. We evaluate our strategy from a quantitative point of view. For that, we use the case of a Human Activity Recognition (HAR) problem consisting of a hydration monitoring system to analyze the suitability of the introduced approach for continuous time-series data. The obtained results show the potential of the presented approach to customizing the participation of the user while, at the same time, improving the baseline results of a non-interactive reference model. In essence, with this work, we seek to increase the users’ role and the system’s customisation ability to result in better user experiences and more effective learning systems in interactive environments at the Edge.

2 Related Work

IML makes it possible for end-users to interact with the learning process to tune the system according to their preferences or even to feed it with more data [3]. In this sense, users' involvement with ML can take many roles in classification tasks, including data curation, learning algorithm tuning, and labeling. The latter is one of the most common approaches, where the final user provides the learning system with sources of truth to personalize it. Additionally, users can participate through feedback on the model's definition and fitting. The personalization of HAR models with user-dependent data illustrates this interaction. Traditionally, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ML-based systems begin with a basic model trained on general data. This model might not be sufficient for generalization based on new data obtained in real contexts. Furthermore, for new users whose data have never been before, it could not suit them well [15]. Thus, in supervised approaches, this means that users can create personalized HAR systems by providing new annotation data [18] or serving as an oracle in Active Learning approaches [23] in which, with the use of sensor data, an interactive approach can enhance the categorization of human activities and motions. For instance, Shahmohammadi et al. [21] proposed an active learning approach to label the sensor data collected by the smartwatch for human activity recognition, conceived to identify 5 commonly performed daily activities. At the same time, in semi-supervised ones, the model can also be fed with raw time-series data [6], as has been previously studied even in federated approaches using mobile devices' inertial sensors [5].

In essence, the idea behind the personalization of ML models is that users iteratively feed the learning system with information (new data) and evaluate the results to enhance following iterations. In this line, several scholars have envisaged how end-users can personalize HAR models. The idea of a smartwatch as an interactive element was also followed by Flutura et al., [9], who presented a human-centered concept of a smartwatch to involve non-expert users in the ML process, giving them control of the personalization of the system. In their work, the smartwatch acted as a cooperative learning Interface from which users could inform the system whether the identified gesture (related to the drinking activity and water intake) was correct or not. This work is aligned with the idea that users could also generalize their own sources of ground truth in the form of labels using their short-term memory on the most recent activity. In this sense, Miu et al. presented an Online Active Learning framework. They concluded that the personalization of HAR models could be bootstrapped without expert supervision or retrospective analysis of the new data [18]. Similarly, other work studied how a user-independent model can be improved incrementally in the activity recognition process and enhanced when personal streaming data is gathered [4]. For that, the literature also addresses that generic models can be rapidly adapted and personalized based on captured user-dependant samples [24].

However, the reviewed works concerning the personalization of ML models have one thing in common: they tend to assume that the final users will always participate in providing new data or labeling the recorded data when queried

by the system. Thus, most IML systems assume that participants are always willing and ready to be involved in this interactive process and provide new sources of truth in the form of labels, but this is not always the case. In fact, the amount of effort required to access such sources of truth appears to be a barrier to encouraging the user to participate in model improvement over an extended period [17]. For this reason, contrary to the reviewed IML approaches, the proposal presented in this work explores the possibility of allowing users to determine their involvement level and willingness to participate in the learning process of the model, aiming at better adapting the system to users' preferences and promoting a long-lasting collaboration.

3 The model cascade approach for Interactive ML

People's involvement with ML can take many roles. Whilst in classic ML, the assumption is that training will be performed only once, in a human-in-the-loop scenario, models can be continuously retrained thanks to user feedback. For example, by providing the learning system with new data. This work presents a hybrid approach that considers different involvement levels and modulates users' participation in this interactive process. In this case, an adaptive configuration based on a cascade of models decides whether to ask or not the user to provide a label for a specific input of data, depending on the user's preferences. This idea of a model cascade was initially presented in [12] in its non-interactive form, conceived to optimize classification tasks by separating complex models into multiple simpler classifiers so that the prediction is made by the one that fits the most to the complexity of the data. In this new proposal, by introducing the interactive factor, it becomes a flexible proposal that can be considered an intermediate approach between a classic ML system (with no user interaction) and a fixed interactive system (with a pre-set interaction level).

To do that, our approach determines the need for human feedback when classifying new data instances based on the prediction's confidence and level of uncertainty. A schematic representation of this system is presented in Fig 1, where the models from 1 to N correspond to successive layers of increasingly complex learning models, which can be selected according to their cost-accuracy trade-off, that is, the balance between its simplicity and optimization capabilities and the resulting classification accuracy [13], [11]. In this case, its complexity is given by the number of features used to train each layer of models.

Initially, one simple and less computationally expensive model is used to classify the input data. Then, depending on the confidence of the prediction, the system can directly classify the new data if the prediction is potentially reliable or try with more complex models until it reaches some required level of confidence. Finally, if none of the different models can provide a reliable prediction, the user may be queried to obtain the actual output. In this configuration, the simplest model acts as a filter, making it less likely to reach the complex ones or the user. From the point of view of optimization, more data can be classified with fewer initial resources.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the interactive model cascade approach. The system inquire the user if none of the N levels of the cascade can provide a reliable prediction.

One difference between the previous implementation of the cascade and this new proposal is that the confidence thresholds t are not static parameters. Here, those thresholds are internally linked with the participation preferences of the user. This way, these thresholds determine how reliable a prediction needs to be to determine whether to accept it or, eventually, interact with the user to obtain the true label for the predicted data sequence. In other words, this interactive cascade balances the interaction frequency of the user (i.e., how many times the system may inquire him or her) and the classification accuracy. This way, lower involvement levels are linked to less restrictive confidence thresholds, whereas higher involvement levels are related to more restrictive confidence thresholds. Therefore, if the confidence requirement is high, it is more likely that a complex data sequence can not be classified by any of the cascade models with the required reliability. In such a case, it would be necessary to query the user about its actual label. Thus, it is expected to have a more significant number of interactions when higher confidence requirements are set. On the contrary, with low confidence requirements, less reliable predictions are admitted as valid. As a result, more data sequences are classified with the cascade models, reaching the final interactive stage less often. However, the classification results can be worse and more potential errors may penalize those users with less interaction. In summary, this adaptive configuration optimizes the classification performance for every new data sequence depending on its complexity, and, at the same time, it adapts the interactive strategy depending on the user's participation willingness.

Once the user is involved in the process by providing new labels for the hardest to classify instances, this new information can eventually be used to improve the classification system by retraining the model with this new data. It is expected that this retraining phase will have an impact on future classification results. In this case, the more involved the user is, the more data will provide

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the interactive retraining loop. User labeled data can be incorporated into the learning process to personalize the model.

to the new model. This way, retraining the system according to new annotated data ultimately results in a more personalized system capable of adapting to each user’s particularities. This idea is similar to the Active Learning strategy in which an oracle (in this case, the user) is asked to label some specific instances of the dataset to include them in the final model. A simplified schematic of this described process is shown in Figure 2.

4 Procedure and Methodology

This section will explain the procedure for evaluating the impact of the presented interactive model cascade. For that, we propose the use case of a HAR problem to assess its applicability for continuous time-series data (e.g., data from accelerometers). For this reason, by means of a dataset created for this purpose, called the Office Hydration Monitoring (OHM) Dataset, we will evaluate the performance of the cascade configuration that will be presented hereafter. This dataset focuses on categorizing the hydration habits of office workers using accelerometer and gyroscope sensors attached to various drink containers (e.g., mugs, bottles, or glasses). The goal of creating this dataset was to have a semi-controlled activity dataset that matches real-world situations. Therefore, the interaction to be recorded was intentionally described very vaguely to the volunteer so that high differences between each subject’s instances of data could be expected. This dataset and additional details about it can be found at [14]. Besides, for this evaluation, we have selected a wide range of supervised ML classifiers: logistic regression (LG), random forest (RF), K-nearest neighbors (KNN), Gaussian Naive Bayes (NB), linear support vector machine (SVM), and multi-layer perceptron (MLP), and Decision Tree (DT). They provide high efficiency for resource-constrained applications [8].

The final configuration of the model cascade is shown in Figure 3. Three levels are included in this setup. The first level i_1 corresponds to a reduced model of 10 features. The second level i_2 increases the number of features up to 50. In both cases, the most representative features were obtained following a filtering feature selection strategy [16]. Lastly, the final model constitutes an interactive stage in which the user may be inquired about the true label of the data if none of the two previous models can provide a prediction that meets the confidence requirements.

Fig. 3. The evaluated model cascade’s configuration including the final interactive stage. T_1 and T_2 are defined according to the participation willingness of the user.

The confidence requirements of each i level depend on the T_i thresholds. Those thresholds are compared against the multi-class loss value of the prediction $L(p, y_{pred})$ defined with the Equation 1:

$$L(p, y_{pred}) = - \sum_{c=1}^M y_{o,c} \log(p_{o,c}) \quad (1)$$

As this value tends to infinity for progressively worse scores, lower loss values are associated with more reliable predictions and higher loss values with less reliable predictions. In this implementation of the cascade, those confidence requirements T_1 and T_2 are not fixed thresholds. Instead, they depend on the potential involvement level of the user. For this reason, three levels of stringency have been defined: low, intermediate, and permissive. Those levels are linked to the $L(p, y_{pred})$ threshold values and intrinsically related to the reported participation willingness of each user. So, the lower the threshold, the more likely the interactive stage will be reached. Therefore, the system will query the user about a specific data sequence.

Those three levels are calculated using a confidence factor that multiplies or divides the baseline thresholds. For comparison, the first threshold T_1 (from model 1 to 2) is set at 0.15. The second one T_2 (from model 2 to 3) is set at 0.40. The confidence factor for each level has been set at 1.25 and 1.50, respectively. This maintains a scale in which initial cascade levels have more restrictive thresholds than successive ones. That is, the first T_1 threshold will become more demanding in terms of confidence in the prediction than T_2 . It should be remarked that both T_1 , T_2 , and the confidence factors 1.25 and 1.50 could be tuned to improve the classification performance of the strategy. However, we have set these values only for comparative purposes, and no other fitting process is performed. This is reflected in Table 1.

Table 1. The correlation between the users’ involvement requirements in the interactive strategy, the confidence, and the threshold values for each of the cascade levels.

Involvement	Confidence level	Threshold value
High	Restrictive	$T_1/1.25 - T_2/1.5$
Medium	Intermediate	$T_1 - T_2$
Low	Permissive	$T_1 * 1.25 - T_2 * 1.5$

5 Analysis and Results

Before analyzing the impact of the model cascade when classifying data from a specific subject, we will first obtain the classification results of the reference model. The reference model is constituted by a single model trained using all the available baseline features (486 initial features). We will obtain those results for all the classifiers in a user-dependent form. In order to do so, a leave-one-subject-out cross-validation evaluation procedure will be followed. This evaluation procedure is an iterative method that uses the available observations of all subjects except one, which is excluded for validation purposes, to train the model. The remaining subject is used to test the prediction capabilities of the trained model. This procedure allows knowing the individualized performance of the baseline model for each user. In this case, since the OHM Dataset consists of 10 independent subjects (or users) and 1000 instances of data, the classification model is trained with the data of 9 subjects (900 instances) and tested with the remaining one (100 instances). This process is repeated 10 times (one subject at a time) to obtain the average classification rates of the system.

The obtained results for this leave-one-subject-out method for the selected classifiers are shown in Table 2. It includes the obtained accuracy results, as its relevance lies in providing an understandable representation of how many errors can be avoided with an interactive strategy. This table shows the results for each of the 10 users included in the OHM dataset. It also includes the average results for all the classifiers and users. It is worth noting how the obtained results vary depending on the user. For example, user 9 presents the highest-ranking result in accuracy (87.71 SD = 4.60). In contrast, user 4 obtains the worst results in the comparison, with an accuracy of 78.29 (SD = 3.14). From the best-case scenario in the classification (user 9) to the worst-case scenario (user 4), there is a loss of 9.43 points for accuracy. The variance observed in the obtained results is indicative of the dispersion of the dataset and the freedom of execution in the actions that every user performed when recording the three target activities (Drink from a mug, Drink from a bottle and Other).

Having understood how user-dependent evaluation affects model performance, we evaluate the impact of replacing the single reference model with a cascade of simple models. The obtained accuracy results for the leave-one-subject-out cross-validation process of the cascade are included in Table ???. It excludes DT as it does not provide a probabilistic prediction nor other parameters suitable to set the confidence. This table also incorporates the results obtained concerning

Table 2. Accuracy results for the leave-on-subject-out evaluation of the reference model, created using all the available features.

Subject	Algorithm							MEAN (SD)
	LG	RF	KNN	NB	SVM	MLP	DT	
User 1	87.00	90.00	78.00	87.00	84.00	90.00	80.00	85.14 (4.70)
User 2	83.00	86.00	77.00	77.00	86.00	84.00	74.00	81.00 (4.89)
User 3	80.00	88.00	74.00	83.00	80.00	81.00	73.00	79.86 (5.14)
User 4	81.00	84.00	76.00	75.00	77.00	78.00	77.00	78.29 (3.14)
User 5	89.00	85.00	77.00	80.00	90.00	86.00	79.00	83.71 (5.08)
User 6	87.00	84.00	76.00	80.00	87.00	90.00	83.00	83.86 (4.74)
User 7	82.00	85.00	81.00	78.00	85.00	83.00	74.00	81.14 (3.97)
User 8	90.00	93.00	74.00	73.00	89.00	92.00	83.00	84.86 (8.39)
User 9	90.00	92.00	83.00	81.00	92.00	91.00	85.00	87.71 (4.60)
User 10	88.00	85.00	77.00	76.00	86.00	91.00	65.00	81.14 (9.00)
MEAN (SD)	85.70 (3.83)	87.20 (3.36)	77.30 (2.83)	79.00 (4.11)	85.60 (4.50)	86.60 (4.90)	77.30 (6.02)	82.67 (2.82)

those instances classified by the first two levels of the cascade (Acc M1 + M2) as well as the number of instances (out of the 100 sequences of data that form the test set) that would reach the interactive stage (Pending Inst.). Those pending instances would not have been automatically classified by the early stages of the cascade (M1 and M2) and would be inquired to the user.

As can be observed, setting a confidence threshold compensates for the potential errors induced by the lighter models. In fact, it increases the accuracy of all the classifiers for those instances that are classified by one of the two initial models (M1 or M2) except NB and MLP. In this case, both classifiers obtain the worst performance, and the cascade approach does not improve the reference results. This may indicate that the applied confidence thresholds are not well calibrated for those algorithms. Still, the rest of the classifiers benefit from the cascading strategy, substantially improving the results of the classified instances.

These results also illustrate how the different thresholds impact the classification rates. The effect of the level of stringency in the confidence requirement is very apparent when comparing the results for each classifier independently. It can be noted how, as the degree of involvement rises and the confidence requirement increases, the classification results also improve. Consequently, fewer data sequences are classified with the required reliability by Model 1 and Model 2, and more of them reach the interactive stage. This means that users would be inquired more often to provide a label for those instances. Hence, the obtained results show the impact of the different involvement levels on the number of instances that reach the user and its consequences on the performance of the model in interactive scenarios.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

In this work, we have presented our vision of a hybrid IML approach where the user is in charge of determining their involvement level and willingness to participate in tuning the learning model for Edge Computing settings. In order to do that, we combine optimization techniques with a probability-based model cascade strategy that simplifies the computation needed to classify new instances of data and modulates the number of times the user is queried to label new data. This cascade determines whether the model is capable enough to provide the most probable outcome for the captured data and the level of certainty of this outcome being true or not. This is done by adjusting the confidence thresholds that rule the classification process according to the desired participation level of the user. This way, the preferences of the user are included as a parameter in the interactive classification process. Consequently, interactive approaches can be adapted to the preferences of the user and result in better user experiences and more effective learning systems.

For the presented use-case, based on a HAR problem with time-series data, the quantitative data obtained throughout the experimental evaluation validates the capabilities of this strategy to (i) modulate the frequency in which the system may inquire users to label new data and (ii) improve the classification capabilities of the system while increasing the efficiency of the process. For future work, we envisage retraining and personalizing models using the user-dependent data provided by the user during the interactive process and assess the potential improvement that successive retraining phases can entail for on the classification results.

Acknowledgements This work has been supported by grant IT1582-22 from Basque Government which recognizes DEUSTEK5 as an excellent research group under the Basque university system. Besides, we acknowledge the Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness of Spain for IoP, under Grant No.: PID2020-119682RB-I00. This work has also been partially supported by the European Commission through the AURORAL project Under Grant No.:101016854.

References

1. Abomhara, M., Køien, G.M.: Security and privacy in the internet of things: Current status and open issues. In: 2014 international conference on privacy and security in mobile systems (PRISMS). pp. 1–8. IEEE (2014)
2. Amershi, S., Cakmak, M., Knox, W.B., Kulesza, T.: Power to the people: The role of humans in interactive machine learning. *Ai Magazine* **35**(4), 105–120 (2014)
3. Bernardo, F., Zbyszynski, M., Fiebrink, R., Grierson, M.: Interactive machine learning for end-user innovation. In: 2017 AAAI Spring Symposium Series. pp. 1–7 (2017)
4. Bettini, C., Civitarese, G., Presotto, R.: Caviar: Context-driven active and incremental activity recognition. *Knowledge-Based Systems* **196**, 105816 (2020)

5. Bettini, C., Civitaresse, G., Presotto, R.: Personalized semi-supervised federated learning for human activity recognition. arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.08094 (2021)
6. Cardoso, H.L., Moreira, J.M.: Human activity recognition by means of online semi-supervised learning. In: 2016 17th IEEE International Conference on Mobile Data Management (MDM). vol. 2, pp. 75–77. IEEE (2016)
7. Dhar, S., Guo, J., Liu, J., Tripathi, S., Kurup, U., Shah, M.: On-device machine learning: An algorithms and learning theory perspective. arXiv preprint arXiv:1911.00623 (2019)
8. Dhar, S., Guo, J., Liu, J., Tripathi, S., Kurup, U., Shah, M.: A survey of on-device machine learning: An algorithms and learning theory perspective. ACM Transactions on Internet of Things **2**(3), 1–49 (2021)
9. Flutura, S., Seiderer, A., Aslan, I., Dang, C.T., Schwarz, R., Schiller, D., André, E.: Drinkwatch: A mobile wellbeing application based on interactive and cooperative machine learning. In: Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Digital Health. pp. 65–74 (2018)
10. Gillies, M., Fiebrink, R., Tanaka, A., Garcia, J., Bevilacqua, F., Heloir, A., Nunari, F., Mackay, W., Amershi, S., Lee, B., et al.: Human-centred machine learning. In: Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems. pp. 3558–3565 (2016)
11. Gómez-Carmona, O., Casado-Mansilla, D., López-de Ipiña, D., García-Zubia, J.: Simplicity is best: Addressing the computational cost of machine learning classifiers in constrained edge devices. In: Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on the Internet of Things. pp. 1–8 (2019)
12. Gómez-Carmona, O., Casado-Mansilla, D., López-de Ipiña, D., García-Zubia, J.: Optimizing computational resources for edge intelligence through model cascade strategies. IEEE Internet of Things Journal **9**(10), 7404–7417 (2021)
13. Gómez-Carmona, O., Casado-Mansilla, D., Kraemer, F.A., López-de Ipiña, D., García-Zubia, J.: Exploring the computational cost of machine learning at the edge for human-centric internet of things. Future Generation Computer Systems **112**, 670–683 (2020)
14. Gómez-Carmona, O., Casado-Mansilla, D.: Office hydration monitoring (ohm) dataset (Apr 2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681206>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681206>
15. Lin, C.Y., Marculescu, R.: Model personalization for human activity recognition. In: 2020 IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications Workshops (PerCom Workshops). pp. 1–7. IEEE (2020)
16. Liu, H., Setiono, R.: Chi2: Feature selection and discretization of numeric attributes. In: Proceedings of 7th IEEE international conference on tools with artificial intelligence. pp. 388–391. IEEE (1995)
17. Masson, C.B., Martin, D., Colombino, T., Grasso, A.: “the device is not well designed for me” on the use of activity trackers in the workplace? In: COOP 2016: Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on the Design of Cooperative Systems, 23-27 May 2016, Trento, Italy. pp. 39–55. Springer (2016)
18. Miu, T., Missier, P., Plötz, T.: Bootstrapping personalised human activity recognition models using online active learning. In: 2015 IEEE International Conference on Computer and Information Technology; Ubiquitous Computing and Communications; Dependable, Autonomic and Secure Computing; Pervasive Intelligence and Computing. pp. 1138–1147. IEEE (2015)
19. Ramos, G., Suh, J., Ghorashi, S., Meek, C., Banks, R., Amershi, S., Fiebrink, R., Smith-Renner, A., Bansal, G.: Emerging perspectives in human-centered machine

- learning. In: *Extended Abstracts of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. pp. 1–8 (2019)
20. Sakr, F., Bellotti, F., Berta, R., De Gloria, A.: Machine learning on mainstream microcontrollers. *Sensors* **20**(9), 2638 (2020)
 21. Shahmohammadi, F., Hosseini, A., King, C.E., Sarrafzadeh, M.: Smartwatch based activity recognition using active learning. In: *2017 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Connected Health: Applications, Systems and Engineering Technologies (CHASE)*. pp. 321–329. IEEE (2017)
 22. Sicari, S., Rizzardi, A., Grieco, L.A., Coen-Porisini, A.: Security, privacy and trust in internet of things: The road ahead. *Computer networks* **76**, 146–164 (2015)
 23. Tegen, A., Davidsson, P., Persson, J.A.: Activity recognition through interactive machine learning in a dynamic sensor setting. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing* pp. 1–14 (2020)
 24. Wijekoon, A., Wiratunga, N.: Personalised meta-learning for human activity recognition with few-data. In: *International Conference on Innovative Techniques and Applications of Artificial Intelligence*. pp. 79–93. Springer (2020)
 25. Worthy, P., Matthews, B., Viller, S.: Trust me: doubts and concerns living with the internet of things. In: *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM Conference on Designing Interactive Systems*. pp. 427–434 (2016)
 26. Zhou, Z., Chen, X., Li, E., Zeng, L., Luo, K., Zhang, J.: Edge intelligence: Paving the last mile of artificial intelligence with edge computing. *Proceedings of the IEEE* **107**(8), 1738–1762 (2019)